

THE ROLE, ESSENCE AND TASKS OF MARKETING AND ADVERTISING ACTIVITIES IN ENTERPRISES

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In today's market conditions, no commercial enterprise can successfully do business without marketing in one form or another and without advertising as an element of it. For many centuries, it has been a constant companion of man and changes with him. [1] We are deeply convinced that the understanding of modern advertising will not be complete without an analysis of the main historical stages of its development. In other words, it doesn't work without the experience and help of advertisers. The power and role of advertising has long been known in the world of business. First of all, advertising usually contains information that is concise, artistically expressed, has an emotional color and conveys the most important facts and information about goods and services to the minds and attention of potential buyers.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Advertising" provides the following definition for Russian participants of the goods market, sellers (advertisers) and buyers (advertisers): reklama (reklama xabari) – "dissemination of information (information) in any form. disclosure by publication, broadcast, public display, public display or communication, reproduction (reprographic reproduction), etc., regardless of advertising, technical or other means. the advertiser, its goods (works, services), their features and characteristics, conditions of production, purchase and use in relation to third (unspecified circle) persons, other that serve to form or support the interest of these persons in the advertiser circumstances, aimed at increasing the competitiveness of its goods (works, services) in the market". Advertising, on the one hand, brings to consumers various information necessary to purchase and use the product. On the other hand, advertising combines its information content with persuasion and suggestion, and has an emotional and spiritual effect on a person. The most common field of advertising activity is commercial advertising, and the subject of advertising influence is goods, commercial enterprises. , are the services provided by these enterprises. At its core, sales advertising is the targeted distribution of information about the consumer characteristics of the product (flyers and proto-newspapers). The invention of printing creates the necessary conditions for the quantitative and qualitative development of advertising.

[2] The proper implementation of advertising in retail stores creates the necessary conditions for more efficient production of products and proper

satisfaction of the needs of the population. The use of exaggerated information about the quality of goods or the declaration of a counterfeit product as a full-fledged product, the use of influence on the basic inclination of a person and other negative motivations are not allowed in commercial advertising.

The design of shops, pavilions and other commercial outlets should meet modern aesthetic requirements, be compatible with the architectural style of the city, and the costs of organizing such advertising should not exceed a reasonable (rational) amount. should add.[3] With the help of advertising, customers find the goods they need faster, buy them with the greatest convenience and with the least loss of time. At the same time, the sale of goods is accelerated, the work efficiency of sales staff increases, and various costs and expenses are reduced. Information about individual trade enterprises, the services they offer, working hours, sales methods and specific features of their activities are less important for the population. organizes the communication between the consumer. It also helps in continuous improvement of products. Another very important role of advertising is that advertising introduces new goods and services to the market, new needs are formed. Advertising is a constant companion of a person and has a great impact on him every day. Whether we like it or not, advertising is part of our culture, and the best examples of it can be attributed to works of applied art. The main requirement of potential buyers and consumers is that advertising should be professional and effective. And to achieve these qualities is no longer possible without considering advertising from the point of view of science. At the same time, advertising is the focus of many disciplines at the same time: communication theory, psychology, marketing, management, mathematics, sociology, etc. Advertising summarizes people's lives and increases their experience. For years, advertising has been criticized for making people want things they don't need. This type of conflict: what customers need or want is not possible. In the advertised market, this is determined by the buyer.

List of references:

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